

An attempt to estimate the annual number of soil samples analysed for the private sector in the European Union

Vassilis Aschonitis¹, Tristano Bacchetti-De-Gregoris², Karina Patricia Prazeres Marques³ and Panagiotis Tziachris¹

¹ Soil and Water Resources Institute, Hellenic Agricultural Organisation-DIMITRA, Thessaloniki, Greece; v.aschonitis@elgo.gr , p.tziachris@elgo.gr

² Soluciones Agrícolas Ecoinnovadoras (SAE INNOVA), Murcia, Spain; tristano@sae-innova.com

³ Esférico MRV Systems, Murcia Spain; karina.marques@esferico2.com

Abstract

Private soil data are important for agronomic decision-making, environmental management, and supporting EU policy frameworks. No harmonised EU-wide register exists for the monitoring of privately funded soil analyses. To address this gap, this study provides a first-order estimate of the annual number of privately commissioned soil samples that are likely analysed in the EU-27. A top-down method was applied for the 2020-2024 reference period using the mean utilised agricultural area and land-use-specific sampling intensity parameters considering assumptions on sampling coverage, composite sample area, and sampling cycle length ranges. The results of the analysis indicate that the annual number of private-sector soil samples in the EU-27 likely ranges from 1.09 million (pessimistic scenario) to 4.35 million (optimistic scenario), with a central estimate of 2.02 million. The findings highlight the potential strategic value of private soil data and the need for technical and legislative frameworks to enable their responsible use to support EU soil and agricultural policy. The estimate of the private-sector samples of this analysis should be interpreted as a market analysis approximation due to the lack of data that would allow proper scientific validation. The reason behind this attempt is to trigger the initiation of political dialog on this issue.

This study was funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme, Grant Agreement No. 101112951 (Driving high-level conversations to shape carbon farming markets and policies - CREDIBLE; <https://www.project-credible.eu/>).

1. Introduction

Soil data produced on behalf of private entities are extremely important since they are used by farmers to assess land suitability for new crops and for precision farming purposes such as fertilization, and by companies to control their environmental footprint and to evaluate the soil as a physical platform for infrastructures. Moreover, private soil data could be used to significantly reduce the cost and time of public-funded soil surveys and to support EU initiatives such as the European Green Deal [1], the Carbon Removals and Carbon Farming (CRCF) [2], the Farm to Fork [3], the Soil Strategy 2030 [4] initiatives, the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) [5] and of course the Soil Monitoring Law [6]. Until now there have not been any attempts to estimate the volume of soil samples on behalf of private entities in the European Union and this is the aim of this study. This attempt aims at indicating a likely high volume of private-sector soil data and to consequently highlight the need for technical and legislative frameworks that will enable their use to support EU initiatives overpassing the restrictions of General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) [7].

2. Methodology

The target variable is the annual number of soil samples whose chemical, physical or biological analysis is commissioned and paid for by private entities in the EU-27. Within this study, “private sector” is defined broadly to include farmers and farmer cooperatives, agribusiness (input suppliers, fertiliser dealers, seed companies), independent agronomic advisors, precision-agriculture service providers, contract farming companies, food processors auditing their supply base, private landowners, and consultancies working for private clients. Samples funded by EU monitoring programs such as LUCAS framework [8,9] or by national environmental soil monitoring networks [10,11,12,13] are treated as a separate publicly funded stream and are used only as a benchmark.

A “sample” is defined as a discrete soil specimen (a composite of auger cores taken from a management zone or field) submitted to a laboratory for generating at least one analytical report. Samples subjected to measurements of multiple parameters (e.g. pH, organic carbon, macronutrients, micronutrients, texture etc) count once. Depth-stratified samples from the same location or zone (topsoil and subsoil) are counted separately, consistent with laboratory invoicing practice. The reference period is the annual average over 2020-2024.

Despite the existence of various registers of agronomic laboratories [14-16] and the Global Soil Laboratory Network (GLOSOLAN) [17], which is quite restricted at EU level, there is not an official EU-wide register of agronomic laboratories while Eurostat does not publish a specific indicator for private soil analyses. For assessing the number of soil samples tested, we apply a top-down method, which is based on agricultural-area \times testing-intensity.

The method starts with the mean utilised agricultural area (UAA) of the EU-27 of the period 2020-2024 [18-23] considering 4 agricultural land use classes (Table 1) (classes were defined based on differences in sampling/testing cycle length) and continues with the application of land-use-specific testing-intensity ranges. For each land-use class three parameters are defined: (i) Coverage: the share of area that is soil-tested within a five-year rolling window, (ii) SampleArea: the average area usually represented by a composite sample, and (iii) CycleYears: the average testing/sampling cycle length in years. The annual sample count is then:

$$N_a = \sum_i (Area_i \times Coverage_i) / (SampleArea_i \times CycleYears_i) \quad (\text{Eq.1})$$

Land-use classes i include arable, permanent crops, intensive grassland and extensive grassland. Intensity parameters (Coverage, SampleArea, CycleYears) ranges are based on national agronomic-advisory guidelines (NL CBGV [24], DE VDLUFA[25], FR COMIFER [26], IE Teagasc [27,28], Nitrates Directive action programmes [29], and CAP conditionality (GAEC 6, GAEC 7) [30,31] (Table 2).

Table 1. Area (Mha) of the four groups of agricultural land uses in the period 2020-2024*.

Land-use class	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	Mean 2020-2024
Arable (cereals, oilseeds, industrial)	98.1	97.8	97.3	98.0	98.3	97.9
Permanent crops (vineyards, orchards, olive)	11.0	11.1	11.2	11.3	11.3	11.2
Intensive grassland (dairy, silage)	20.0	19.8	19.6	19.4	19.2	19.6
Extensive grassland / pastures	28.3	28.3	28.3	28.2	28.2	28.3
EU-27 (4 classes)	157.4	157.0	156.4	156.9	157.0	156.9

*The four classes are built from Eurostat in a way that is fully consistent with the 2020 Farm Structure Survey anchor. Arable area is taken from *apro_cpshr*; permanent crops from *apro_cpsh1*; total permanent grassland from *ef_oluft*; the intensive/extensive grassland split is derived from livestock unit (LU) stocking densities (LU/ha of forage area) using a ≥ 1.5 LU/ha threshold [18-23].

Table 2. Range of parameters for implementing the top-down method which is based on agricultural-area \times testing-intensity. Ranges reflect variability across Member States and between low- and high-input systems.

Land-use class	Mean area (Mha) 2020-2024	Coverage share (5-yr)	Area of composite sample (ha)	Cycle (yrs)
Arable (cereals, oilseeds, industrial)	97.9	45–60 %	5–10	4–5
Permanent crops (vineyards, orchards, olive)	11.2	30–55 %	2–5	3–5
Intensive grassland (dairy, silage)	19.6	20–35 %	5–10	4–6
Extensive grassland / pastures	28.3	3–8 %	10–20	5–8

3. Results

2.1. Estimations of private sector soil samples

Applying the method described above using Tables 1 and 2, three intensity scenarios (Low, Central, High) were considered for each of the three parameters of Coverage, Composite area and Cycle (Table 3). The intensity scenarios were applied in such way to provide three different calculations: the lowest pessimistic scenario, the central and the highest optimistic scenario (Table 4). The lowest pessimistic scenario uses the low value of coverage and the high values of the other two variables while the

highest optimistic scenario is applied in the opposite way. The central scenario is based on the central values of the parameters. Considering the results of Table 4, **the EU-27 volume of private-sector soil samples ranges between ~1 to 4.3 million per year over the 2020–2024 reference period with a central value approximately ~2 million samples per year.**

Table 3. Intensity scenarios of Coverage, Composite area and Cycle parameters for applying Eq.1. based on Table 2.

Land-use class	Mean Area 2020-2024 (Mha)	Coverage (share)			Area of composite sample (ha)			Cycle (years)		
		Low	Central	High	Low	Central	High	Low	Central	High
Arable crops	97.9	45.0%	52.5%	60.0%	5.0	7.5	10.0	4.0	4.5	5.0
Permanent crops	11.2	30.0%	42.5%	55.0%	2.0	3.5	5.0	3.0	4.0	5.0
Intensive grassland	19.6	20.0%	27.5%	35.0%	5.0	7.5	10.0	4.0	5.0	6.0
Extensive grassland	28.3	3.0%	5.5%	8.0%	10.0	15.0	20.0	5.0	6.5	8.0

Table 4. Estimations of private-sector samples per year in EU-27 according to three scenarios.

Land-use class	Million samples/year		
	Lowest (pessimistic)	Central	Highest (optimistic)
Arable crops	881,100	1,522,889	2,937,000
Permanent crops	134,400	340,000	1,026,667
Intensive grassland	65,333	143,733	343,000
Extensive grassland	5,306	15,964	45,280
EU-27 TOTAL	1,086,140	2,022,586	4,351,947

2.2. Comparison versus the publicly funded soil samples' volume of the LUCAS framework

Since the main EU instrument for soil monitoring is the LUCAS framework, a comparison can be made with the estimated values of the private sector of Table 4. The amount of soil samples analyzed in the context of LUCAS surveys of 2009/2012 (19,969 samples in 2009 + 2,034 in 2012) [32], 2015 (21,859 samples) [33], 2018 (18,984 samples) [34] and 2022 (38,000 samples) [35] are approximately in total 103,846 samples over a period of 13 years. The mean annual rate of analyzed samples is estimated at ~7988 samples per year. Considering the samples per year of Table 4 of the three scenarios Low, Central, High, the respective “private vs. public LUCAS samples” ratios are estimated ~136:1, 253:1, 545:1. This result shows that the soil samples per year of the private sector may be two orders of magnitude more than those of the LUCAS framework. This indicates that the possible and controlled inclusion of the private-sector soil samples in the LUCAS framework would lead to an extremely high enrichment of soil information/monitoring at EU level.

4. Discussion - Conclusion

The estimate of the private-sector samples of this analysis should be interpreted as a market analysis approximation. No harmonised EU-wide register of privately commissioned agronomic soil analyses was identified, and several of the largest laboratory networks do not publish annual agronomic sample throughput in a consistent form. As a result, the resulting range is informative for order-of-magnitude purposes.

The comparison with publicly funded soil-monitoring networks should be interpreted carefully. Public programs such as LUCAS are designed for representativeness and long-term trend detection, whereas private agronomic sampling is demand-driven and management-oriented. The private-to-public ratios presented here are therefore best understood as a contrast in sampling volume and operational purpose, not as a comparison of analytical depth, policy relevance, or scientific value.

Overall, the analysis supports the conclusion that privately commissioned agronomic soil testing in the EU-27 is extremely large and likely lies in the low single-digit millions of samples per year. This result should be considered by the EU to support technical and legislative frameworks that will enable their use to support EU initiatives overpassing the restrictions of GDPR.

5. References

1. European Union. Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions. European Green Deal. Eur. Council 2019. Available online: <https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/policies/european-green-deal/> (last accessed on 17 April 2026).
2. European Union. Regulation (EU) 2024/3012 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 November 2024 establishing a Union certification framework for permanent carbon removals, carbon farming and carbon storage in products. Off. J. Eur. Union 2024, L. Available online: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2024/3012/oj> (last accessed on 17 April 2026).
3. European Union. Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions A Farm to Fork Strategy for a fair, healthy and environmentally-friendly food system. Eur. Comm. 2020, COM(2020) 381 Final. Available online: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A52020DC0381> (last accessed on 17 April 2026).
4. European Union. Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions EU Soil Strategy for 2030. Eur. Comm. 2021, COM (2021) 699 final. Available online: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A52021DC0699> (last accessed on 17 April 2026).
5. European Union. Regulation (EU) 2021/2115 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 2 December 2021 establishing rules on support for strategic plans to be drawn up by Member States under the common agricultural policy. Off. J. Eur. Union 2021, L435, 1–139. Available online: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2021/2115/oj> (last accessed on 17 April 2026).
6. European Union. Directive (EU) 2025/2360 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 12 November 2025 on soil monitoring and resilience (Soil Monitoring Law). Off. J. Eur. Union 2025, L. Available online: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/dir/2025/2360/oj> (last accessed on 17 April 2026).

7. European Union. Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data (General Data Protection Regulation). Off. J. Eur. Union 2016, L119, 1–88. Available online: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2016/679/oj> (last accessed on 17 April 2026).
8. JRC European Soil Data Centre (ESDAC) – <https://esdac.jrc.ec.europa.eu/projects/lucas> (last accessed on 17 April 2026).
9. JRC European Soil Data Centre (ESDAC) – general portal. <https://esdac.jrc.ec.europa.eu/> (last accessed on 17 April 2026).
10. INRAE / GIS Sol – Réseau de Mesures de la Qualité des Sols (RMQS). The soil quality monitoring network for French soils (RMQS): state of progress and first results. Hal-02753780. <https://hal.inrae.fr/hal-02753780> (last accessed on 17 April 2026).
11. Johann Heinrich von Thünen Institute, Federal Research Institute for Rural Areas, Forestry and Fisheries. <https://www.thuenen.de/en/institutes/forest-ecosystems/> (last accessed on 17 April 2026).
12. Knotters et al., (2022). Changes in organic matter contents and carbon stocks in Dutch soils, 1998–2018, *Geoderma*, 414, 115751, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoderma.2022.115751> (last accessed on 17 April 2026).
13. AGES – Österreichische Agentur für Gesundheit und Ernährungssicherheit GmbH: Soil survey. <https://www.ages.at/en/environment/soil/soil-survey> (last accessed on 17 April 2026).
14. EUROLAB – <https://www.eurolab.org/structure> (last accessed on 17 April 2026).
15. DAKKS – <https://www.dakks.de/en/accredited-bodies-search.html> (last accessed on 17 April 2026).
16. WEPAL – <https://participants.wepal.nl> (last accessed on 17 April 2026).
17. GLOSOLAN – <https://www.fao.org/global-soil-partnership/glosolan/en/> (last accessed on 17 April 2026).
18. Eurostat (2022). Farm Structure Survey 2020 – results overview (UAA 157.4 Mha EU-27). https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Farmers_and_the_agricultural_labour_force_-_statistics (last accessed on 17 April 2026).
19. Eurostat – Metadata of the Farm Structure Survey (ESMS, ef_sims). https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/cache/metadata/en/ef_sims.htm (last accessed on 17 April 2026).
20. Eurostat – Crops production in EU standard humidity, annual data (apro_cpshr). https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/apro_cpshr/default/table (last accessed on 17 April 2026).
21. Eurostat – Permanent crops by age, density and area (apro_cpsh1, ef_lpc_cp). https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/ef_lpc_cp/default/table (last accessed on 17 April 2026).
22. Eurostat – Main farm land use by agricultural size of the farm (ef_oluft). https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/ef_oluft/default/table (last accessed on 17 April 2026).
23. Eurostat – Agri-environmental indicator: livestock density (aei_ef_ls). https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/aei_ef_ls/default/table
24. CBGV – <https://www.bemestingsadvies.nl/producten-en-links/> (last accessed on 17 April 2026).
25. VDLUFA – Fachgruppe II (Soil / soil analysis), Germany. <https://www.vdlufa.de/fachgruppen-40-2/fg-ii/?lang=en> (last accessed on 17 April 2026).
26. COMIFER – https://platform.nutri-checknet.eu/recommendation_systems/13/comifer (last accessed on 17 April 2026).

27. Teagasc – Soil Fertility Report 2024. <https://teagasc.ie/wp-content/uploads/2025/05/Teagasc-Soil-Fertility-Report-2024-1.pdf> (last accessed on 17 April 2026).
28. Teagasc Soil Fertility Dashboard and Report 2025 – <https://teagasc.ie/wp-content/uploads/uploads/media/website/environment/soil/Teagasc-Soil-Fertility-Report-2025.pdf> (last accessed on 17 April 2026).
29. Council Directive 91/676/EEC (Nitrates Directive) – text and Article 10 reporting obligation. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:31991L0676> (last accessed on 17 April 2026).
30. European Commission – DG AGRI. Common Agricultural Policy: Conditionality (GAEC 1–9). https://agriculture.ec.europa.eu/common-agricultural-policy/income-support/conditionality_en (last accessed on 17 April 2026).
31. European Commission – DG AGRI. Nutrients / low-input farming (CAP). https://agriculture.ec.europa.eu/cap-my-country/sustainability/environmental-sustainability/low-input-farming/nutrients_en (last accessed on 17 April 2026).
32. JRC European Soil Data Centre (ESDAC) – <https://esdac.jrc.ec.europa.eu/content/lucas-2009-topsoil-data> (last accessed on 17 April 2026).
33. JRC European Soil Data Centre (ESDAC) – <https://esdac.jrc.ec.europa.eu/content/lucas2015-topsoil-data> (last accessed on 17 April 2026).
34. JRC European Soil Data Centre (ESDAC) – <https://esdac.jrc.ec.europa.eu/content/lucas-2018-topsoil-data> (last accessed on 17 April 2026).
35. JRC European Soil Data Centre (ESDAC) – <https://esdac.jrc.ec.europa.eu/content/lucas-2022-topsoil-data> (last accessed on 17 April 2026).